

DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONAL TOURISM: FACTORS AFFECTING THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN FUTURE PROFESSIONALS IN TOURISM

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Abstract

The socio-political changes faced by Russia force universities to adjust the theoretical training and practical skills of students. These changes need to focus on the development of domestic tourism in Russia. In one hand, this brings about the need for a large number of specialists in domestic tourism and, on the other hand, for systemic adjustments to the training of future specialists in the organization of tourism. Thus, the study aims to identify factors in the formation of professional competence in future specialists in the organization of regional tourism in higher education. These factors are established through analysis of scientific sources and the results of an expert survey. We have identified two groups of the major factors that need to be taken into consideration when training specialists. The first group of factors affects the content of training and, in particular, includes targeted formation of student motivation to master professional skills and abilities in developing regional tourist products using national experience. The second group influences the methods of training (e.g. including the use of group training methods and interactive technologies). Conclusions show that the effectiveness of the formation of the professional competence of future specialists in the organization of regional tourism will be ensured primarily by targeted formation of students' motivation to master professional skills and abilities to form a regional tourist product and the use of national experience of formation and implementation of regional tourist products in the activities of tourist enterprises. Moreover, such formation will be facilitated by the use of group teaching methods and interactive technologies in teaching the development of regional programs, as well as by opportunities to take internships in the tourism support system at national enterprises.

Keywords: Domestic tourism; Expert survey; Student internship; Organization of tourism.

DESENVOLVIMENTO DO TURISMO REGIONAL: FATORES QUE AFETAM A FORMAÇÃO DE COMPETÊNCIAS PROFISSIONAIS EM FUTUROS PROFISSIONAIS DO TURISMO

Resumo

As mudanças sócio-políticas enfrentadas pela Rússia obrigam as universidades a ajustar a formação teórica e as competências práticas dos estudantes. Estas mudanças têm de se concentrar no desenvolvimento do turismo interno na Rússia. Por um lado, isto traz a necessidade de um grande número de especialistas em turismo doméstico, e por outro, de ajustamentos sistêmicos na formação de futuros especialistas na organização do turismo. O estudo visa identificar fatores na formação de competência profissional em futuros especialistas na organização do turismo regional no ensino superior. Estes fatores são estabelecidos através da análise de fontes científicas e dos resultados de uma pesquisa com experts no tema. Identificam-se dois grupos dos principais fatores que precisam de ser tomados em consideração na formação de especialistas: o primeiro relacionado ao conteúdo da formação e, em particular, a formação orientada da motivação dos estudantes para dominarem as competências e capacidades profissionais no desenvolvimento de produtos turísticos regionais utilizando a experiência nacional. Já o segundo grupo influencia os métodos de treinamento (por exemplo, com o uso de métodos de treinamento em grupo e tecnologias interativas). Pode-se concluir que a eficácia da formação da competência profissional dos futuros especialistas na organização do turismo regional será assegurada principalmente pela formação orientada da motivação dos estudantes para dominar as habilidades e habilidades profissionais para formar um produto turístico regional e o uso da experiência nacional de formação e implementação de produtos turísticos regionais nas atividades das empresas turísticas. Além disso, tal formação deverá ser facilitada pelo uso de métodos de ensino em grupo e tecnologias interativas no ensino do desenvolvimento de programas regionais, bem como por oportunidades de fazer estágios no sistema de apoio ao turismo em empresas nacionais.

Palavras-chave: Turismo doméstico; Inquérito de peritos; Estágio para estudantes; Organização do turismo.

DESARROLLO DEL TURISMO REGIONAL: FACTORES QUE AFECTAN A LA FORMACIÓN DE LA COMPETENCIA PROFESIONAL DE LOS FUTUROS PROFESIONALES DEL TURISMO

Resumen

Los cambios sociopolíticos a los que se enfrenta Rusia obligan a las universidades a ajustar la formación teórica y las habilidades prácticas de los estudiantes. Estos cambios deben centrarse en el desarrollo del turismo interno en Rusia. Por un lado, esto conlleva la necesidad de un gran número de especialistas en turismo interno y, por otro, de ajustes sistémicos en la formación de los futuros especialistas en la organización del turismo. El estudio tiene como objetivo identificar los factores en la formación de la competencia profesional en los futuros especialistas en la organización del turismo regional en la educación superior. Estos factores se establecen mediante el análisis de fuentes científicas y los resultados de una encuesta a expertos. Se han identificado dos grupos de los principales factores que hay que tener en cuenta en la formación de especialistas. El primer grupo afecta al contenido de la formación y, en particular, incluye la formación dirigida a la motivación de los estudiantes para dominar las habilidades y capacidades profesionales en el desarrollo de productos turísticos regionales utilizando la experiencia nacional. El segundo grupo influye en los métodos de formación (e.g. usando métodos de formación en grupo y tecnologías interactivas). Se puede decir que la eficacia de la formación de la competencia profesional de los futuros especialistas en la organización del turismo regional estará garantizada principalmente por la formación específica de la motivación de los estudiantes para dominar las habilidades y capacidades profesionales para formar un producto turístico regional y el uso de la experiencia nacional de formación e implementación de productos turísticos regionales en las actividades de las empresas turísticas. Además, dicha formación se verá facilitada por el uso de métodos de enseñanza en grupo y tecnologías interactivas en la enseñanza del desarrollo de programas regionales, así como por las oportunidades de realizar prácticas en el sistema de apoyo al turismo en empresas nacionales.

Palabras clave: Turismo nacional; Encuesta de expertos; Prácticas de estudiantes; Organización del turismo.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Global experience demonstrates that a necessary condition for the successful development of tourism is adequate staffing (Duborkina et al, 2021). Russian tourism is in dire need of qualified personnel to provide high-quality tourist services (Zvyagintseva et al, 2020). At present, it appears reasonable for the Russian tourism sector to shift from sporadic and haphazard work with personnel to a balanced personnel policy (Ukhina, 2018). Incidentally, Dusenko (2013) notes that staff training for the tourism industry is of value for the state and society and defines the leading principles of educational policy in the interests of the individual, society, and the country.

The need for the improvement of workforce training is currently determined by the following inconsistencies. First and foremost, these are the contradictions arising between the growing demand of Russia's population for tourist services and the inability of the tourism industry to satisfy it (Dudin et al., 2017). Furthermore, the need to improve staff training is caused by a conflict between changes in the competitive landscape and insufficient competence of personnel in different areas of tourism (management, economic, environmental, legal, and professional) (Mukhamadieva & Polupanov, 2017).

Thus, taking into consideration the current new transitional socioeconomic conditions in Russia, particularly in its tourism sector and the establishment of Russia's educational system, the objectives of improving the organization of training of tourism specialists and the development of their professional and business skills appear as relevant and contributive to the further development of this sector.

The results of previous studies in Russia (e.g. Pereverzev, 2020; Timoshenko, 2020) suggest that the work of a specialist in tourism expands further than organizational management and economic issues. A tourism specialist has to possess knowledge of various aspects including social, humanitarian, cultural, historical, legal, aesthetic, recreational, and environmental (Pastukhova & Grudistova, 2018).

On the other hand, professionalism in the tourism industry has to also encompass benevolence, knowledge of psychology, and the ability to independently operating and provision of various types of tourist services, which involves a broader scope of fundamental knowledge (Karpova, Voloshinova, & Khoreva, 2019) focused on the development of the experience economy (Çoban & Ardiç Yetiş, 2019).

In this context, the goal of the present study is to determine factors that affect the formation of professional competence in future specialists in the organization of tourism in the sphere of regional tourism at universities.

To achieve this, we have defined intermediary objectives are as follows: a) to identify the major factors in the formation of professional competence in future specialists in the organization of regional tourism in universities; and b) to rank the determined factors and establish the ones most significant for the effective development of domestic tourism in Russia.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

The current place and justification of the advisability of introducing practice-oriented learning technologies in the professional training of future specialists in tourism has been the subject of studies in Russia in recent years (Cherniakova, 2012). To these technologies the researcher attributes teamwork and approximation to practice through role-playing; provision of training based on the collaboration of universities with tourism companies through the dual system; improvement of professional expertise in the workplace; an expansion of the elective component of educational programs, which will contribute to the individualization of the educational process; granting more autonomy to universities in the development of vocational training programs; transformation of the content of training; diversification of areas and specialties in the tourism sector (Cherniakova, 2012).

Given the variety of conditions in different countries, there have been developed different models for planning the educational process in the field of tourism, including domestic tourism, having some of them – e.g. the British, American, and German – being highlighted as educational models, and serving as reference to other countries.

The British model illuminates two approaches to training. The first one is represented at the lower levels of education (secondary vocational and vocational-technical), the programs in which are more professionally-oriented and designed to provide students with specific practical skills in the sphere of hospitality (Baum & Teixeira, 2001). The second approach to the study of hospitality is offered by the higher education sector and focuses on supplying students with a set of tools that develop their analytical skills. These educational programs are typically four-year and, nearly without exception, one year (or more) needs to be allocated for internships in the tourism industry (Fidgeon, 2011).

Tourism education programs in the United States are also classified into two types. The first one is academic education at the undergraduate and postgraduate levels, where tourism is offered as a separate major or as part of the student's chosen program of study (Airey et al., 2015). These are typically four-year programs, and the curricula mostly

consist of a traditional core curriculum related to hospitality or recreation and resorts (Fidgeon, 2010). The second approach offers professional development through certified programs designed for those already working in the industry at the managerial level (Innui, Wheeler, & Lankford, 2006). These programs are usually designed in the form of professional internships, which consist of 12-16 weeks of full-time employment or six months of part-time employment (on-the-job) (Jamal, Taillon, & Dredge, 2011).

Education in tourism management in Germany is carried out through a combination of full-time and part-time courses and higher-level educational programs, which are provided by educational institutions in three different degrees (Kim & Jeong, 2018). Firstly, there are educational institutions that provide entry-level knowledge and business skills, which are formed in two-year courses offering the qualifications needed to access higher education in the tourism industry (Çakar & Çizel, 2015). Secondly, there are higher vocational education institutions with three- or four-year courses in tourism, travel, and hotel management, which combine the study of economics, law, financial management, marketing, business and personnel management, and taxation with a specialization in tourism (Mondok, 2015). The ratio of these disciplines varies significantly across different institutions. Finally, there are universities that (mainly) provide postgraduate degrees

in the form of one year of full-time study or three years of part-time study (Volgger & Pechlanner, 2015).

Meanwhile, the training in tourism specialties offered in Russia does not fully comply with the modern requirements for the formation of professional competence in the organization of tourism. According to Ruban (2018), this is due to the limited amount of academic hours for specialized disciplines and too much time for cycles of general and special courses and disciplines, the list of which demonstrates the multidisciplinary nature of the tourism sphere.

That multidisciplinary characteristic of tourism has to be considered when harmonizing requirements for vocational training and educational programs in tourism in universities (Pirogova, 2018). Constant adjustment of educational programs necessitates monitoring of trends in the national tourism industry, the leading among which currently is domestic tourism (Amosov & Ashinova, 2021).

Thus, given the aforementioned context, the purpose of this paper is to identify factors in the formation of professional competence in future specialists in the organization of regional tourism in higher education in Russia.

The table 1 summarizes and organize the main models used to guide this study, their concepts (variables) and characteristics.

Table 1. The main models used to guide this study, their concepts (variables) and characteristics.

Model of Reference	Concepts	Caracteristics
▪ British	▪ secondary vocational and vocational-technical education	▪ lower levels of education; ▪ short-term; ▪ programs more professionally-oriented and designed to provide practical skills;
	▪ higher education	▪ higher level; ▪ Long-term (4 years); ▪ fer a set of tools that develop their analytical skills; ▪ Integration (1 year) with industry through internships;
▪ USA	▪ academic education	▪ undergraduate and postgraduate levels; ▪ long-term (4 years);
	▪ professional development	▪ professional internships ▪ short-term (12-16 weeks) ▪ part-time employment; ▪ certified programs designed for those already working in the industry at the managerial level
▪ Germany	▪ educational institutions that provide	▪ entry-level knowledge and business skills; ▪ short-term (two-year courses); ▪ intermediary qualifications needed to access higher education in the tourism industry;
	▪ higher vocational education institutions	▪ Medium to long-term (three- or four-year courses); ▪ Curricula: on tourism, travel, and hotel management) or another disciplinar field with a specialization in tourism;
	▪ universities	▪ medium to long-term (1 year of full-time or 3 years of part-time study); ▪ advanced degrees (mainly – postgraduate degrees); ▪ long-term period (4 years);

Source: own elaboration based on the literature review (e.g. Baum & Teixeira, 2001; Wheeler, & Lankford, 2006; Fidgeon, 2010; Fidgeon, 2011; Jamal, Taillon, & Dredge, 2011; Airey et al., 2015; Volgger & Pechlanner, 2015; Mondok, 2015; Kim & Jeong, 2018).

3 METHODS

To determine the factors of the formation of professional competence in future specialists in the organization of regional tourism, an expert assessment of the circumstances (Iudina et al., 2022; Karmanov et al., 2020) affecting the level of students' professional training was conducted.

The study was conducted in April of 2022 through a delphi panel (Pimentel & Carvalho, 2020; Rosa & Anjos, 2022), which was constituted by three main phases. The first stage was a pilot survey that covered 33 experts, of which 17 were university professors in the specialty "Organization of tourism" and 16 were social partners (employees of travel agencies). The experts were presented with an open-ended questionnaire with the question: "*name the circumstances that, in your opinion, affect the level of professional competence of future specialists in the organization of tourism in regional tourism*".

At the second phase of the study, the experts were asked to rank the most often mentioned factors of the formation of professional competence in future specialists in the organization of regional tourism.

For additional verification of the reliability of expert assessments, we selected a control factor similar to those identified by experts in the first stage of the study. The equivalence of the assessments of similar factors

(the ones made by the experts and control) will indicate the reliability of expert evaluations.

At the third stage of the study, a matrix of the results of experts' assessment of factors in the formation of professional competence of future specialists in the organization of regional tourism was compiled. The matrix allowed us to draw conclusions on the leading factors in the formation of professional competence in future specialists in organizing regional tourism programs.

For a more objective analysis of the data obtained in the expert survey, the consistency of expert opinions was assessed via mathematical processing of the results using Kendall's coefficient of concordance (W):

$$W = 12S/n^2(m-1)$$

where: S – the sum of squared deviations of all ranks of each of the factors of professional competence formation from the average value; n – the number of experts; m – the number of evaluated factors of professional competence formation.

4 RESULTS

The results of the pilot study point to 10 factors most often noted by the respondents (Table 2).

Table 2. Factors of the formation of professional competence in future specialists in the organization of tourism in the sphere of regional tourism.

No.	Factors	%*
C1	Category 1 - Targeted formation of students' motivation to master professional skills and abilities in forming a regional tourist product	69.2%
C2	Category 2 - Striving for self-improvement	53.8%
C3	Category 3 - High professionalism and creativity of the faculty	53.8%
C4	Category 4 - Opportunities for internships in the tourism support system at national enterprises; constant communication with employers and the possibility of internships and work while studying	76.9%
C5	Category 5 - Use of national experience in developing and implementing regional tourist products in the work of tourism companies; the use of management methods for selecting directions and options for the development of tourist enterprises at the regional level	84.6%
C6	Category 6 - Use of group training methods and interactive technologies as a means of teaching how to form a team for the development of regional tourism programs	84.6%
C7	Category 7 - Wider introduction of the legal aspects of tourism in the learning process; ensuring the professional orientation of the content of legal disciplines	61.5%
C8	Category 8 - Introduction of the information component of the organization of tourist activity; factors of the introduction and use of information technology in tourism; practice of the skills of working with online resources	69.2%
C9	Category 9 - Emphasis on entrepreneurial skills and abilities; teaching a systematic course on starting and running a private business	53.8%
C10	Category 10 - Development of students' research activities	61.5%
C11	Category 11 - <i>Need for constant renewal of knowledge (control factor)</i>	

Source: compiled according to the results of the expert survey.

* Percentage of expert mentions. ** C – category (e.g. C1 – category 1).

To further confirm the validity of expert evaluations, we chose a control factor of "Need for constant renewal of knowledge (control factor)" (Table 1). This factor in the ranking system (Table 2) scored

247.5 points, which is close to the 249 points earned by the "Striving for self-improvement" factor. Thus, the need for constant renewal of knowledge is undoubtedly represented by the desire for self-improvement.

Based on the expert ranking, we determined the most significant factors in the formation of professional

competence of future specialists in the organization of tourism in the sphere of regional tourism (Table 2).

Table 2. Matrix of the results of expert assessment of the factors of professional competence formation in future specialists in the organization of tourism in the field of regional tourism.

Experts/factors	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI
1	3	9	10	1	2	5	4	7	8	11	6
2	3	9	4	2	1	7	5	8	10	11	6
3	5	9	6	2	3	1	4	8	10	11	7
4	4	8	6	1	3	2	7	9	5	11	10
5	1	11	9	5	4	2	3	7	10	6	8
6	5	3	10	2	1	4	8	7	6	11	9
7	7	8	2.5	2.5	1	6	4.5	11	10	9	4.5
8	2	8	6	4	3	1	5	7	9	11	10
9	2	7	6	3	1	4	8	5	9	11	10
10	3	5	9	1	4	2	6	11	10	8	7
11	8	1	9	7	3	6	2	10	5	11	4
12	1	11	4	5	3	6	2	10	9	7	8
13	6	7	11	5	3	1	2	4	10	8	9
14	3	9	10	1	2	5	4	7	8	11	6
15	5	3	10	2	1	4	8	7	6	11	9
16	7	8	2.5	2.5	1	6	4.5	11	10	9	4.5
17	4	8	6	1	3	2	7	9	5	11	10
18	1	11	9	5	4	2	3	7	10	6	8
19	1	11	4	5	3	6	2	10	9	7	8
20	6	7	11	5	3	1	2	4	10	8	9
21	3	9	10	1	2	5	4	7	8	11	6
22	2	7	6	3	1	4	8	5	9	11	10
23	3	5	9	1	4	2	6	11	10	8	7
24	8	1	9	7	3	6	2	10	5	11	4
25	5	3	10	2	1	4	8	7	6	11	9
26	7	8	2.5	2.5	1	6	4.5	11	10	9	4.5
27	2	8	6	4	3	1	5	7	9	11	10
28	3	9	4	2	1	7	5	8	10	11	6
29	5	9	6	2	3	1	4	8	10	11	7
30	4	8	6	1	3	2	7	9	5	11	10
31	1	11	9	5	4	2	3	7	10	6	8
32	3	9	4	2	1	7	5	8	10	11	6
33	5	9	6	2	3	1	4	8	10	11	7
Σ	128	249	232.5	96.5	79	121	156.5	265	281	322	247.5
Rank	4	8	6	2	1	3	5	9	10	11	7

Source: compiled according to the results of expert ranking; the value of the concordance coefficient $W = 0.78$ ($p < 0.01$), indicating the consistency of expert opinions.

The results of expert evaluation point to the following factors as the leading ones in the formation of professional competence of future specialists in the organization of tourism in regional tourism:

- 1) The use of Russian experience in developing and implementing regional tourist products in the work of tourism companies; the use of management methods for selecting directions and options for the development of tourist enterprises at the regional level;
- 2) Opportunities for internships in the tourism support system at national enterprises;
- 3) The use of group training methods and interactive technologies as a means of teaching how to form a team for the development of regional tourism programs.

5 DISCUSSION

Regarding the category 1 (C1) – *targeted formation of students' motivation to master professional skills and abilities in forming a regional tourist product* –, the first factor pointed to by the experts is the use of national experience in the development and implementation of regional tourist products in the work of tourism businesses (as well as the use of management methods for selecting directions and options for the development of tourist enterprises at the regional level. For future specialists in the organization of regional tourism, it is critical to know how to make use of previous experience to quickly and effectively form tourist products and collaborate with counteragents to

attract customers and funds for the development of new tourist destinations (Potekhina et al., 2022).

These conclusions are further emphasized by studies indicating that specialists in tourism need to be able to work with logistics companies (Ukhina et al., 2022), tourism infrastructure service providers (Ivanova et al., 2022), banking institutions (Panasenko et al., 2022), and public authorities (Melnikova et al., 2019). The knowledge and skills acquired by students when studying specialized disciplines have to be applied in nature (Danilova et al., 2022). Therefore, during the COVID-19 pandemic, it is advisable to make the fullest use of practice-oriented tasks based on previous experience, which would form students' understanding of their future professional functions.

In the categories C2 and C3 (*striving for self-improvement; high professionalism and creativity of the faculty, respectively*), it was seen that the next most significant factor in the formation of professional competence of future specialists in organizing regional tourism, according to our findings, is the opportunity for internships in the tourism support system at national enterprises, constant communication with employers, and the possibility of internships and work while studying).

Thus, during their training, future specialists in tourism have to acquire the practical skills of designing and compiling tours and excursions, organizing different types of tourism, developing communication skills, and learning to solve conflicts and other professional situations at the workplace (C4 - *opportunities for internships in the tourism support system at national enterprises; constant communication with employers and the possibility of internships and work while studying*). In this vein, Pereverzev (2020) argues that practical training in the real tourism environment is the main direction for improving their professionalism.

Educational and industrial internships allow students to get acquainted with the work of enterprises and institutions, their organization, management, and planning. Interns obtain knowledge about the content and features of their future professional practice and study the regional characteristics of tourism (C5 - *use of national experience in developing and implementing regional tourist products in the work of tourism companies; the use of management methods for selecting directions and options for the development of tourist enterprises at the regional level*) (Danilova et al., 2022).

Analyzing the shortcomings of the organization of internships, Pereverzev (2020) emphasizes the declarative nature of contracts of higher education institutions with tourist organizations; the assignment of students to certain services of a tourist enterprise and

their mastery of the technologies of individual departments, rather than of the work experience as a whole; a low level of experience acquired by students, which is caused by them performing simple tasks and the practical lack of industry workers' intentions to structure the volume of operations performed by students.

The findings of A. Mondok (2015) show that most training programs for the tourism industry pay great attention to the practical training of future tourism specialists.

In particular, the administration of the Disney World theme park in the US has developed internship programs for students of tourism universities for a whole academic year, depending on the form of study, on the basis of their resorts in California and Florida (Disney College Program) (Jamal et al., 2011). The program provides the familiarization of its participants with the structure of the park, the range of professions in it and the methods of work, the study of the system of attraction, as well as seminars and conferences with park managers, the preparation of individual projects by trainees with the assistance of the main managers, and independent activities. The program offers all the necessary conditions for the representatives of universities to monitor the activities of interns. Special presentations on the Disney College Program have been organized at US institutions of higher education.

The third factor chosen by the experts is the use of group training methods and interactive technologies as a means of teaching how to form a team for the development of regional tourism programs.

Group methods of teaching and interactive technologies are effective methods of raising the level of students' professional training (C6 - *use of group training methods and interactive technologies as a means of teaching how to form a team for the development of regional tourism programs*). After all, the main goal of the organization of any educational process is to create conditions conducive to acquiring new knowledge (Melnikova et al., 2019), reveal creative potential (Sokolova & Sergeeva, 2021), and form students' life competencies (C7 - *wider introduction of the legal aspects of tourism in the learning process; ensuring the professional orientation of the content of legal disciplines*) (Gladilina et al., 2022).

Group teaching methods and interactive technologies are the tools aimed at developing students' active interaction, cognitive interest, and creativity in making independent decisions (C8 - *introduction of the information component of the organization of tourist activity; factors of the introduction and use of information technology in tourism; practice of the skills of working with online resources; C9 - emphasis on entrepreneurial skills and abilities;*

teaching a systematic course on starting and running a private business). These instruments also provide an enabling environment for the successful absorption of educational material (C10 - *development of students' research activities*; C11 - *need for constant renewal of knowledge*) (Timoshenko, 2020).

Research suggests that the advantages of these methods are shaped by the following factors (Cherniakova, 2012; Pivneva et al., 2022; Rabadanova et al., 2022): a fundamental change in the goals of higher education in the specialty of regional tourism; the requirements of the social order (which prioritizes the cultural and spiritual growth of students and personality-oriented learning aimed at the subjective activity of students); developmental learning, which is not limited to knowledge, but also includes informational (knowledge, skills, and abilities act as the objects of assimilation) and activity components (constant interaction of the student with the subject; knowledge, skills, and abilities are considered as a form of activity aimed at personal development).

6 CONCLUSION

The effectiveness of the formation of the professional competence of future specialists in the organization of regional tourism will be ensured primarily by targeted formation of students' motivation to master professional skills and abilities to form a regional tourist product and the use of national experience of formation and implementation of regional tourist products in the activities of tourist enterprises. Secondly, the formation of professional competence is facilitated by the use of group teaching methods and interactive technologies in teaching the development of regional tour programs, as well as by opportunities to take internships in the tourism support system at national enterprises.

Despite of the efforts made by the researchers, this research has some limitations regarding the sample, which is a small one and it doesn't represent the population of the study. Thus, the results found here can refer just to the sample analyzed. Moreover, the analysis presented is based on the experts' perceptions, what may not fit to the reality itself – and even may, in some cases, differ significantly from that. On the other hand, due the broadness and recurrency of the topics presented, the authors are inclined to think – despite their restrictions aforementioned – that the results show are mainly convergent and representative of reality.

Further research is advisable to focus on the development of methods for the formation of professional competence of future specialists in the organization of regional tourism, as well as in the

different contexts and backgrounds, which may differ and show particularities according to the educational level and or national tourism development level.

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Table. CRediT author statement.

Term	Definition	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	+	+	+
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	+	+	+
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components	+	+	+
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs	+	+	+
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data	+	+	+
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	+	+	+
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	+	+	+
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	+	+	+
Writing - Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	+	+	+
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or post-publication stages	+	+	+
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation	+	+	+
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team	+	+	+
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution	+	+	+
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication	+	+	+

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